

EFFECTS OF CRYSTALLINE MORPHOLOGIES ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCING POLYMERIZED CYCLIC BUTYLENE TEREPHTHALATE COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Carbon/pCBT composites were prepared by utilizing the modified film stacking technique. Three crystalline morphologies of polymerized cyclic butylene terephthalate were crystallized at different temperatures. Tensile, flexural, short beam shear and impact tests were evaluated. The relationship between crystalline morphology, process and mechanical properties of carbon/pCBT composites was investigated.

1 Introduction

Low viscosity cyclic butylene terephthalate (CBT) oligomer is a very promising material for a new generation of thermoplastic and composite applications. CBT is readily polymerized to linear high molecular weight poly(butylene terephthalate (termed as pCBT) in the presence of tin or titanium catalysts [1] within few minutes (3-5 min at 190 °C). Recent interests in CBT are not only for its recycling concept fiber to manage the growing waste polymer problem and it also provides promising characters to stimulate the development of thermoplastic composites.

CBT has some important advantages for thermoplastic composites processing: water like low viscosity, the capability of rapid polymerization into polybutylene terephthalate (pCBT) which will from cyclic oligomer transformed into linear high-molecular weight engineering thermoplastic, there have not any low-molecular weight byproducts evolution during the polymerization and have an ability to be processed like thermosetting resins such as resin transfer molding [2].

In 2006 Mod Ishak etc. [3], studied the rheological properties of pCBT and found a drastic reduction in

pot life at polymerization temperature above 200 °C. When higher polymerization temperature was used such as 210 °C, the pot life was only 1 to 2 minutes which resulted in problem on the composite process with poor impregnated the reinforcing fabric. In 2009 Baets etc. [4] reported the molecular weight of pCBT increased with increasing the polymerization temperature. The highest molecular weight of pCBT was polymerized at 240 °C. Thermal degradation occurred and led to a lower molecular weight pCBT at polymerization temperature of 250 °C. Hakme et al. [5] studied the polymerization and crystallization kinetics of CBT by dielectric sensing. They found that, simultaneous polymerization and crystallization (type I) occur below 200 °C, polymerization is followed by crystallization (type II) above 200 °C, and only polymerization (type III) occurs above 220 °C. That is the crystallization behavior of pCBT not only affected by the crystallization condition but also influenced by the polymerization condition. In order to simplify the crystallization mechanism of pCBT, category type III samples were polymerized at 230 °C for 30 min. to allow complete polymerization firstly.

As far as the application of CBT for continuous fiber reinforced composites is concerned there are only a few published works on this subject. Parton and Verpoest et al. [2, 6] first prepared unidirectional glass fiber reinforced pCBT composites by using resin transfer molding (RTM) technique. The Results shown that the mechanical properties of the pCBT composites were not affected in fiber dominated orientations. The transverse strength of the pCBT composites was lower than the matrix's tensile strength due to the brittleness of the pCBT matrix. Baets et al. [7-8] reported that the copolymerization

of pCBT/PCL hinders the crystallization of pCBT. This pCBT/PCL copolymer led to a much tougher material, for both unfilled material and for glass fiber reinforced composites. Mohd Ishak et al. [9] prepared glass woven fabric reinforced pCBT composites by using compression molding technique. The results shown that low viscosity CBT facilitated the penetration of the resin through the fabric and also exhibited good interfacial properties. Maeder et al. [10] investigated the interphase between glass fibers and pCBT resins and found that the interfacial bond strengths of glass/pCBT composites varied depending on the sizing formulation and properties.

Until now, only Glass and Basalt fiber have been used as reinforcement for pCBT composites [2-4, 6, 7, 11]. Interestingly, carbon fiber, a reinforcement of great renown for composite materials has not been reported for pCBT composites.

In our previous study [12] on the isothermal crystallization of pCBT polymerized at 230°C has catalogued four morphologic features: usual negative spherulite, unusual spherulite, mixed birefringence spherulite coexisting with boundary crystals, and highly disordered spherulitic crystallines corresponding to the crystallization temperatures. Polymerized CBT (pCBT) provides interesting crystalline characteristics which may have strong influence on the properties of pCBT composites. It is therefore, our objective was to investigate the effect of process conditions on the crystalline morphology and performance of the resulting carbon/pCBT composites. The evaluated mechanical properties of the carbon fiber/pCBT composites involved in tensile, flexural, short beam shear and impact testing.

2 Experiment

2.1 Materials

In this study, CBT pellets (Grade: 160) purchased from Cyclics (Schenectady, NY; www.cyclics.com) were used. This CBT is produced using a Butyl tin chloride dihydroxide (XB3) catalyst with an average molecular weight $M_w = (220)_n$ ($n=2\sim7$) for the purpose of engineering plastic and composite applications. CBT was dried in a vacuum oven for overnight at 85 °C and kept in a desiccator until further use. The reinforcement used in this study was 3K carbon fiber (HTA40, Toho Tenax America, USA) in twill weaving structure.

2.2 Sample preparation

This study presents a modified film stacking technique [13] to produce high quality impregnated and void free carbon/pCBT composites. At first, the CBT matrix was prepared into a thin film form (thickness of 300 μm) using compression molding at 150 °C for 1 min, at a pressure of 5 MPa. This was followed by quenching the matrix in water by covering it with Teflon films. The carbon/pCBT prepreg with average thickness of 300~350 μm was prepared using the procedure: laid-up one layer of carbon fabric on CBT thin film at 150 °C for 3 min under a pressure of 8 MPa followed by quenching in water with the covering of Teflon films. The carbon/pCBT composites were prepared by stacking eight layers of prepregs at polymerization temperature: 230 °C for 30 min at a pressure of 12 MPa to allow complete polymerization, followed by quench to the desired crystallization temperature ($T_c = 185$ °C, 195 °C, and 210 °C). Based on the crystallization kinetics study [12], the holding time for complete crystallization were 20 min for $T_c = 185$ °C, 40 min for $T_c = 195$ °C, and 120 min for $T_c = 210$ °C. Then, the composite samples were followed by slow cooling to room temperature and demolded. In this experiment, the fiber volume fractions of the carbon fiber/pCBT composites were approximately 55%

2.3 Mechanical Test

In this study, a universal testing machine (AG-100kNX, Shimadzu, Japan) was used to perform the tensile, flexural and interlaminar shear properties evaluations at room temperature. Tensile tests were performed on the carbon/pCBT composites in accordance with ASTM-D3039. Three-point bending and short beam shear (SBS) tests were done according to ASTM D790 and D2344, respectively, to estimate the flexural and apparent interlaminar shear strength (ILSS). Flexural specimens in 100 mm long and 12 mm wide by 2 mm thick were cut from the carbon/pCBT composite plates. A span length of 64 mm assured a span-to-depth ratio of 32, and a crosshead speed of 3.4 mm/min was adopted. The SBS specimen of 22.8 x 6 x 3.8 mm³ was placed on two cylindrical supports of 2 mm in diameter and bent by a cylindrical head of 6 mm in diameter at the centre of the specimen. The tests were conducted with a crosshead rate of 1 mm/min and a

span/thickness ratio of 4. The Izod impact test was performed at room temperature according to ASTM D256 on a pendulum impact tester (CPI, Atlas electric devices, USA) at impact energy of 2.6 J. The average values were derived from five parallel tests for each material. To investigate the reinforcing effects on the failure modes in carbon/pCBT composites, the failure and cross-sectional area of the damaged samples was examined using an optical microscope and SEM.

2.4 Morphology observation of carbon/pCBT composites

The morphology of carbon/pCBT composites were determined by using a polarized light microscope equipped with a Linkam THMS 600 hot stage (Linkam, Epsom, UK). A quartz plate was used to determine the sign of the birefringence of the pCBT spherulite. In this way the first and third quarters of the sight were yellow and the second and fourth were blue when the forms were negative, while a reversed arrangement of the quarters were observed for positive forms. A small piece of CBT added within high tenacity carbon fibers were squeezed between two microscope slides and then inserted into the hot stage. Nitrogen was used as the purge gas in the hot stage during all measurements and thermal treatments. Each sample was heated to 230°C at a rate of 130°C/min, held for 30 min to allow complete polymerization, and then cooled to the desired T_c at a rate of 60°C/min, which $T_c = 185^\circ\text{C}$, 195°C , and 210°C .

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Morphology of carbon/pCBT composites

Fig.1 shows the PLM images of crystalline morphologies of pCBT during crystallization at different T_c . For the samples prepared at $T_c = 185^\circ\text{C}$ and 195°C , the unusual and mixed type birefringence spherulite morphologies were revealed, respectively. The spherulite size was larger for the sample prepared at $T_c = 195^\circ\text{C}$ compared with that of T_c at 185°C . As for the samples at $T_c = 210^\circ\text{C}$, the spherulite morphology was lost and highly disordered spherulitic crystallites were observed. Please notice that well-defined spherulitic boundary and boundary crystals were found in the samples prepared at $T_c = 185$ and 195°C . The spherulitic boundary line disappeared gradually as the crystallization

temperature increased from 195 to 200°C and the boundary crystals vanished at T_c greater than 200°C [12]. For all the three conditions, the transcrystalline phenomenon was clear observed. Contrast with samples for $T_c = 185$ to 195°C , a well-defined transcrystalline was revealed as pCBT crystallization at 210°C . This is the first time that a well-defined transcrystalline is clearly revealed in pCBT polymer under quiescent crystallization condition. Owing to this mutual interaction between fiber and pCBT matrix, good interfacial properties would be highly expected.

3.2 Effects of T_c on the mechanical properties of carbon/pCBT composites

Figure 2 shows typical tensile stress-strain curves of carbon/pCBT composites at different T_c . All the curves displayed significant yielding and post yield strain hardening, indicating the reinforcing effect and structural homogeneity for the carbon/pCBT composites. The major failure modes, as shown in Fig.3, are long-range delamination (Fig. 3a), and multifilament bundle breakage (Fig.3b). Due to the twill-woven interlaced structure, stress concentration took place on the fiber bundles around the interlaced point and led to shear breakage of the fiber bundles (Fig. 3c). When the bundle split or experienced breakage, the released fractured energy dissipated with large amounts of long-range delamination, resulting in stress vibration. The post-yield modulus represents the reinforcing efficiency and interfacial bonding of the carbon/pCBT composites, increased with increasing of the T_c and results in the tensile strength increased. Table 1 summarized all the tensile properties and the degree of crystallinity for carbon/pCBT composites at different T_c . All of the tensile properties of the carbon/pCBT composites increased with the T_c increased. The carbon/pCBT sample crystallized at 210°C , exhibited the highest tensile modulus of 21.0 GPa, and strength: 426.4 MPa, with 7 and 25% enhancement, respectively, when compared to the composite sample at $T_c = 185$. As for the results for yield strength and post-yield modulus, composite sample at $T_c = 210^\circ\text{C}$ exhibited the best performance, whereas, a lower results were obtained in the samples prepared at $T_c = 185$ and 195°C . Please noticed, the spherulite morphology of the 210°C sample was highly disordered crystallites without clear spherulitic boundary and boundary crystals. This matrix behaves like homogeneous material without phase separation.

Morphology with clear boundary and boundary crystals may act as defect which caused the decreasing of tensile properties.

Fig. 4 shows the typical flexural stress-strain curves of the carbon/pCBT composites at different T_c . Similar to tensile results; all samples demonstrated a severely vibrating curve before the final catastrophic fracture. Two failure modes: compressive and tensile failures were found in Fig. 5. The failures on the tension surface involved fiber bundles breakage, cracks and short range delamination while that on the compression surface was local buckling. Buckling was manifested as fiber micro-buckling and ply-level buckling. Ply-level buckling resulted in short range delamination of the outer ply. All samples did not collapse within the crosshead limit. This reveals the prevention ability from crack propagation by the reinforcing carbon fabric. Similar to the tensile result, composite sample at $T_c = 210^\circ\text{C}$ exhibited the highest flexural modulus: 45.1 GPa, was attributed to higher degree of crystallinity (44%). The flexural strength for composite sample at $T_c = 210^\circ\text{C}$ was 508 MPa, whereas samples at $T_c = 185$ and 195°C were 403~407 MPa, with 26% enhancement. The results manifested crystalline morphology strongly influencing the mechanical properties of carbon/pCBT composites. Composite sample with highly disordered crystallites without spherulitic boundary and boundary crystals demonstrated the best tensile and flexural properties.

The notched Izod impact properties for the carbon/pCBT composites were shown in Table 1. The impact energy for composite sample at $T_c = 210^\circ\text{C}$ was 809 J/m, whereas samples at $T_c = 185$ and 195°C were range from 774~779 MPa, with 5% enhancement. The carbon/pCBT composites failed with tensile and compressive failures, and did not break apart (Fig. 6). This impact failure revealed the prevention ability of the crack propagation by the reinforcing woven fabric. When the impactor encountered the carbon/pCBT specimen, the fiber bundle pull-out and breakage occurred around the notched side first, while compressive force built up around the other side of specimen and caused short range delamination. The impact failure modes were matrix fracture, delamination, and fiber bundle breakage (pull-out and kink). A close view on the impacted carbon/pCBT composite at tensile side as shown in Fig. 7, presented that all the pull-out fiber bundles were coated with pCBT resin. The results

demonstrated good interfacial bonding between carbon fiber and pCBT. The cohesive failure occurred at the pCBT matrix was attributed to the brittleness of pCBT resin [6].

The ILSS is a non-fiber dominated property and influenced by both the matrix and interface properties. When the composite sample was load subjected, the initiate cracks normal to the loading direction either at the matrix/fiber interface or in the matrix. A low ILSS is therefore an indication of either poor fiber/matrix interfacial properties or matrix brittleness.

There were no visible failures found in the ILSS tested carbon/pCBT composite samples. These may be preceded by less obvious, local damage modes such as transply cracking. The interlaminar shear strength for the sample of $T_c = 210^\circ\text{C}$, displayed the highest ILSS: 59.7 MPa. Remember that the transcrystalline morphology and cohesive failure were found in all carbon/pCBT composite samples in this study. No much difference in the ILSS (54~59 MPa) manifested the effects of transcrystalline on the interfacial adhesion.

4. Conclusion

In this study, carbon/pCBT composites were prepared by utilizing the modified film stacking technique. Results showed that the mechanical properties of the carbon/pCBT composites were strongly affected by the crystalline morphologies and crystallinity. A well-defined transcrystalline is clearly revealed in pCBT polymer under quiescent crystallization condition. Morphology with clear boundary and boundary crystals may act as defect which caused the brittleness of the pCBT matrix. The carbon/pCBT sample crystallized at 210°C with highly disordered spherulitic crystallites and without spherulitic boundary line and the boundary crystals, exhibited the highest mechanical properties.

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Table 1 Mechanical properties of the carbon/pCBT composites at various T_c .

T_c	185°C	195°C	210°C
Tensile modulus (GPa)	19.7±1.5	20.1±1.9	21.0±2.5
Tensile strength (MPa)	340±8	384±8	426±11
Yield strength (MPa)	72.1±4.4	70.0±8.6	87.5±1.0
Post-yield modulus (GPa)	8.68±1.1	8.56±1.4	9.51±0.6
Flexural modulus (GPa)	43.6±2.4	42.4±1.0	45.1±3.3
Flexural strength (MPa)	403±8	407±9	508±13
Impact energy (J/m)	779±4	774±8	809±8
ILSS (MPa)	54.1±1.2	55.2±1.0	59.7±0.4
Crystallinity (%)	33.8	37.9	44.7

Figure 1 Crystalline morphologies of the carbon/pCBT composites at different T_c , (a) 185 °C, (b) 195 °C, (c) 210 °C.

Figure 2 Typical tensile stress-strain curves of the carbon/pCBT composites at different T_c .

Figure 3 Typical tensile failure modes for the carbon/pCBT composites.

Figure 4 Typical flexural stress-strain curves of the carbon/pCBT composites at different T_c .

Figure 5 Typical flexural failure modes for the carbon/pCBT composites.

Figure 6 Typical impact failure modes for the carbon/pCBT composites. (a) side view, (b) compressive side, (c) top view.

Figure 7 SEM images for the impact failure carbon/pCBT composites at tensile side showing (a) fiber pull-out, (b) cohesive failure at the fiber/matrix interphase.